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DEVELOPMENT OF A MEASUREMENT SYSTEM FOR HOT FLOW ACOUSTIC TESTS

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ABSTRACT

This research activity is carried out in order to develop a measurement system for performing acoustic measurements in thermally hostile environment, representative of the turbine exhaust in an aircraft engine, for liner characterization purposes.

A fundamental step for the development of an optimal liner design process is the validation of the treatment performance in a controlled environment simulating the actual operating conditions, and specifically the turbine exit. Since common microphones with on-board amplifiers are very sensitive to the temperature and it is essential to protect them if the experimental conditions experience temperatures greater than 70 °C (operating temperature limit), the development of advanced measurement technique is a key aspect. At the Department of Industrial Engineering of the University of Florence (DIEF), a dedicated research activity is ongoing. The proposed measurement system leverages the concept of acoustic measurements via recessed microphones: it consists of microphones installed at the end of cylindrical cavities fully or partly occupied by a sound absorbing material that isolates the microphones from the hot flow and, at the same time, damps the resonances excited in the cavities [1]. The frequency response function (FRF) of such devices has to be experimentally estimated, hence a dedicated test rig has been produced.

As a starting point, several microphones holders having different materials and geometries have been investigated, and the FRF has been measured through tests at room temperature and without air flow. Results, even if preliminary, let conclude that the measurement technique is promising but an appropriate selection of the arrangement is crucial for its effectiveness.

INTRODUCTION

The noise generated by an aircraft can be divided into two main components, the propulsion noise and the airframe noise, and the first one is the main contributor at certain certification points. The radiated acoustic emission is typically controlled by reducing its generation at source, or by limiting its propagation through noise control systems, such as acoustic liners, installed along the bypass duct and in the intake of the engine. The use of absorbers represents a promising way to reduce also the Low-Pressure Turbine (LPT) noise, but the working conditions at the exit of the core duct are clearly different from those of the 'cold duct' and require a dedicated activity for the fine tuning of the prediction methodology. The characterization of the acoustic liners is based on their acoustic impedance, defined as the ratio between the acoustic pressure and the particle velocity. The verification of the noise reduction effectiveness of such systems relies on different techniques.

The measurement of the normal incidence impedance in absence of flow is usually carried out by means of a Kundt's tube, which is a consolidated and standard procedure, recognized at international level [2], whose main advantage is the ease of use. It is based on a two microphones method that allows to distinguish the incident wave and the reflected wave propagating along a waveguide, through the measurements of the pressure amplitude and phase at two measurement positions.

Most recent systems for liners' investigation adopt long square-sectioned rig equipped with microphones' arrays that can be mounted directly on the wall facing the liner, on the side walls, or on the portions of the duct placed upstream or downstream of the test-section containing the liner [3]. These rigs can evaluate the liner performance in presence of grazing air flows.

For LPT-focused investigations, the impedance shall be estimated under test conditions representative of actual

turbine exhaust, therefore test rigs operating at high flow speed and temperature shall be adopted.

ACOUSTIC MEASUREMENTS AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

The techniques for dynamic pressure measurements at high temperature can be grouped into at least three distinct categories:

- Use of active sensor cooling;
- Use of sensors withstanding high temperatures;
- Use of waveguide systems to move the sensor away from the high temperature region.

Starting from the first one, the active air or water cooling systems allow the use of standard sensors in high temperature applications but imply also a significant addition of equipment and complexity for the overall system. The adoption of cooled pressure transducers directly available on the market avoids the development of the cooling system but has, besides the cost, the disadvantage of creating cold spots on the conduit walls, therefore an array of these microphones could have an important impact on the characteristics of the flow within the duct.

Another possible method to perform pressure measurements in thermally hostile environment is represented by temperature resistant sensors, for example devices whose electronics are made up of silicon circuits printed on insulating material. In this way, each electronic component is isolated from the others, eliminating the undesired effects due to the parasitic currents that affect the electronics at temperatures above 125 °C. Thanks to this technology, the transducers can be used with temperatures up to 235 °C. The main disadvantage of these systems is the high cost per channel. Analogously, ceramic piezoelectric devices could be used up to 375 °C at sensor's diaphragm. The main drawbacks can be the spatial resolution, i.e. the higher sensor dimension, the noise floor and the cost per channel.

The waveguide systems using the Infinite Pressure Line (IPL) concept for remote microphones are highly considered because they rely on standard microphones and can be easily deployed, even if the manufacturing of the pressure lines has to be very accurate, especially at the duct connections. The setup of IPL [4, 5, 6, 7, 8] could become difficult when the number of measurement points of the array rises. Needs for calibration and the limited bandwidth can be counted as drawbacks of this method.

Arrays of recessed microphones have been investigated [9] in wind tunnels to reduce the flow noise effects in flush mounted configurations. Devices have been developed [10] in such a way that a porous membrane is mounted in front of the microphone, with the dual objective of keeping the flow outside the cavities and, at the same time, permitting the transmission of the sound waves.

Considering the above assessments, at DIEF a research activity took place to develop an acoustic measurement system for high temperatures, based on the microphone recessing concept.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

To briefly describe the adopted investigation methodology, a plane wave propagation inside a rectangular test section is hereafter considered. The acoustic pressure field is given by the superposition of a downstream traveling or incident wave, and an upstream traveling or reflected wave, and can be expressed as:

$$p(x_i) = Ae^{jkx_i} + Be^{-jkx_i} \quad (1)$$

$$u(x_i) = \frac{A}{Z_c} e^{jkx_i} + \frac{B}{Z_c^*} e^{-jkx_i} \quad (2)$$

$$k = \alpha - j\beta \quad (3)$$

where A and B are the amplitudes of the incident and reflected waves, respectively, k is the complex wave number, x is the axial coordinate along the propagation direction and Z_c is the characteristic impedance of the medium. In case the medium is air, considering no losses, $k = k_0 = \frac{\omega}{c}$ is the free field wavenumber and $Z_c = \rho c$ is the characteristic impedance of a plane wave. In case the medium is a sound absorbing material like a porous or fibrous medium, k and Z_c are complex quantities and can be provided by correlations or semi analytical models [11].

In order to characterize the measurement system under investigation, its FRF shall be experimentally estimated. The FRF can be estimated according to Eq. (4):

$$H_{1,2} = \frac{p(x_2)}{p(x_1)} = \frac{G_{12}}{G_{11}} \quad (4)$$

where G_{12} is the cross-spectral density measured between the investigated device and a reference signal.

Another important parameter to be estimated is the reflection coefficient which can be experimentally assessed by the Two Microphones Method (TMM). The TMM utilizes the measured transfer function between two positions in the tube. The measured transfer function ($H_{1,2}$) can be related to the reflection coefficient R by using Eq. (5):

$$R = \frac{H_{12} - e^{-jk\Delta x}}{e^{jk\Delta x} - H_{12}} * e^{2jkx_1} \quad (5)$$

The material properties, such as the acoustic impedance and sound absorption coefficient, can be derived from the reflection coefficient. The specific impedance can be obtained from Eq (6).

$$Z = Z_c * \frac{1 + R}{1 - R} \quad (6)$$

TEST BENCH

To experimentally characterize the behavior of the system with recessed microphone and insulating shield, a dedicated test rig has been manufactured with the following specifications:

- The dimensions of the cross-section allow the propagation of the plane wave only for frequencies up to 10 kHz
- The materials guarantee the possibility of using the bench with high temperatures
- To characterize the behavior of the measurement system in the presence of flow, the rig foresees the passage of air (a compressor provides the air supply).

Figure 2 1. Fixing grain - 2. Mounting support - 3. Microphone chucking system - 4. Locking nut - 5. Microphone cable - 6. Microphone - 7. Sound absorbing filling (only for Meta Aramid Felt) - 8. Brass holder for the insulating material sample

It has been decided to make the test bench duct with a squared section in order to facilitate the installation of the microphones with the diaphragm flush with the wall, without creating any geometric discontinuity. The main pipeline was built with a squared section having a 15 mm side, to meet the aforementioned acoustic requirement. The speaker is placed at the end of a 200 mm long tube and inclined at 45° to the duct wall.

Further, the rig has been manufactured in stainless steel, to allow its use at high temperatures, and leverages a modular design approach, to achieve the greatest possible versatility in view of future upgrades and developments.

A detailed description of the rig is given in the reference [1]. In this rig, the FRF of the device under test (DUT) is estimated with respect to a reference microphone (RM) installed flush with the duct wall exactly in front of the DUT. A picture of the rig with its main components is shown in Figure 1.

The microphone is installed on a mounting support, which is basically a cylinder able to fit the measurement slot on the rig, and sealed by means of a chucking system enabling, when it is loosened, the possibility to change the microphone distance from the duct wall: cavities up to 30 mm, fully or partially filled by insulating material, can be considered by simply sliding the microphone inside its guide.

The internal diameter of the mounting support is 10 mm so that it can be housed inside the brass cylinder used to hold the selected insulating material. If requested, a protective wire mesh can be installed in front of the holding system to protect the insulating material from the grazing air flow.

Figure 1 1. Speaker - 2. Wave generator - 3. Amplifier - 4. Temperature data acquisition system - 5. Microphones data acquisition system - 6. Measurements section - 7. Anechoic termination

In the present work, preliminary tests at room temperature and in the absence of flow are presented.

RECESSED MICROPHONE MOUNTING SYSTEM

The characterization of the FRF of various recessed microphone configurations [13, 14] relies on a dedicated support allowing different shielding solutions, in terms of insulation materials and considered thicknesses, and various distances of the microphone from the wall of the conduit.

Figure 2 sketches the mentioned recessed-microphone holder.

FEASIBILITY CONSIDERATIONS

By considering the aforementioned motivations, the measurement device suitable for hot flow acoustic measurements under development at DIFP relies on the recessed microphones concept. The use of cylindrical cavities, partially filled with a porous insulating material, responds to different needs. In particular, it is worth noting that:

- The insulating material must shield the sensor from the hot environment and prevent the direct entry of a hot gas flow into the cavity;
- By mounting the microphones within cavities, resonances are expected in the FRF; the insulating material has to provide an appropriate damping to attenuate the amplitude of these peaks;
- The system must also preserve the continuity of the duct surface as much as possible, minimizing the impact on the acoustic field inside the duct.

As a preliminary feasibility study, the thermal control of the measurement system has been considered, based on a simple analytical model. In Figure 3, on the left, the scheme of the system is shown, in which the acoustic pressure is measured by the microphone installed at the end of a cavity, partially filled with a porous insulating material with low thermal conductivity. On the right, the results of a one-dimensional calculation to estimate the relationship between temperatures on the diaphragm of the microphone and the thicknesses of the empty air cavity and insulating

material are reported. It is worthy to mention that the heat transfer through the cylindrical surface of the cavity is assumed to be negligible in this analysis, therefore the assumption is to have a perfect thermal insulation. The heat transfer can occur just in the vertical direction, through the insulation material and the air cavity.

The results, even if preliminary, are encouraging and confirm the possibility to keep the microphone temperature within acceptable limits. Due to the strong hypothesis in the model, the need for cooling is expected to be necessary at the backside of the measurement system but, if the thermal insulation is good enough, just the natural convection or a limited forced convection could be sufficient to guarantee the sensor's integrity with a reasonable safety margin. Detailed investigations are ongoing.

Figure 3 Results of a one-dimensional calculation to estimate the relationship between temperature on the microphone diaphragm and the thickness of air and insulating material

INSULATION MATERIAL

The selection of the insulating material is a crucial aspect to be addressed because it is necessary to comply with several requirements. It can be noted that the material must satisfy the following characteristics:

1. Low thermal conductivity
2. Low thermal expansion
3. Low density
4. Low electrical conductivity

The thermal conductivity of the material plays a vital role because it limits the heat flux towards the sensor, while the reduced thermal expansion delivers low mechanical stresses to the mounting system during the operations at hot temperatures. In addition, from the acoustic propagation perspective, it is highly recommended to find a means which possesses a low density and open-pored structure to facilitate the passage of sound waves. Finally, poor electrical conductivity can be useful to work around electrical disturbances, which would be detrimental to a good measurement.

From the above, a trade-off problem has to be resolved, where different priorities must be satisfied to identify a highly performing support, able to meet all the design constraints.

Three materials have been selected as insulation means: glass wool (GW), meta-aramid felt (AF) and ceramic felt (CF) (Table 1).

Table 1 Insulation materials specifications

Specification	Materials		
	GW	AF	CF
Thermal Conductivity [W/ (m.K)]	0.04	0.32	0.38
Max. Working Temp. [°C]	400	1000	1260

PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATION

The general measurement arrangement is shown in Figure 4. The test bench foresees three couples of microphones, installed at three axial positions:

- Section D: 150 mm upstream of section C
- Section C: where the RM and the DUT are installed for FRF measurement
- Section B: 150 mm from anechoic termination for estimating the coefficient of reflection

Figure 4 Test section; from left to right: Flange connecting the test section to the anechoic termination (A); Pair of staggered microphones (B); calibration section with reference microphone and recessed microphone (C); pair of staggered microphones (D); speaker support flange (E); flange for the connection with an air supply (F)

A preliminary investigation has been performed to assess the goodness of the microphones' mounting system and the rig in general. The DUT has been installed flush at the duct wall, without any insulating material or cavity in front of it, and its measurements have been compared with the RM. Ideally, the two sensors should provide the same response. Referring to Figure 5, the FRF in terms of phase shows just minor deviations from the RM. The same applies to the amplitude since the curve starts deviating from 5 kHz (Figure 6). Anyway, the discrepancies between the DUT and the RM are significantly low. Such deviations can be explained considering that a weak standing wave exists in the duct even though the effectiveness of the anechoic termination was already checked [1] and resulted to be very high but, obviously, not perfect. Consequently, the small deviations are probably the result of small misalignment errors in the microphones' positions, i.e. the curve of the picture 5 and 6 are nothing but the FRF of two slightly staggered mics in the axial direction within a weak standing wave pattern. Nevertheless, the considerably small deviations measured confirmed the possibility to use the test bench for the calibration of the DUT with an acceptable accuracy. Further, to verify the impact of the wire mesh on the acoustic response of the measurement system, two microphone configurations have been considered: one with the sensor set back by 20 mm with respect to the duct wall, with the wire mesh installed but without any absorbing material in the cavity; the other one identical to the first but without the wire mesh. The obtained FRFs have been compared. Figure 7 shows an image of the system and the

amplitudes of the two transfer functions. It is worth noticing that a non-dimensional frequency is used on the abscissa which makes the curves independent w.r.t. small differences in testing conditions, i.e. temperature differences and the actual depth of the cavity considering the end correction. The results highlight, on one hand, the expected resonances due to the cavities in front of the diaphragms; on the other hand, they confirm that, in absence of grazing flow, the wire mesh does not influence the response of the system.

Figure 5 Comparison of the transfer function between the microphones in positions 0 and 1 in terms of phase

Figure 6 Comparison of the transfer function between the microphones in positions 0 and 1 in terms of amplitude

Figure 7 Wire mesh impact on measurements with a 20 mm empty cavity

TESTS WITH SOUND ABSORBING MATERIALS

Three insulating material holders, made from brass cylinders, as shown in Figure 8, were prepared and filled with a glass wool felt.

Figure 8 Cylinders with glass wool

Due to the fibrous nature of the GW, its density and consequently its acoustic properties change within a large range depending on how much it is compressed inside the holder. A preliminary investigation allowed to select a limited range of densities which are suitable for the purpose of this investigation. Thus, different amounts of GW have been inserted in each of the cylinders according to Table 2:

Table 2 Glass wool samples

n°	Diameter [mm]	Length [mm]	Density [kg/m ³]
1	7	10	rho1
2	7	10	rho2 = 1.5 * rho1
3	7	10	rho3 = 0.65 * rho1

The tests on specimens #1, #2 and #3 were carried out in a frequency range from 1.5 kHz to 10 kHz, by using an incremental step of 100 Hz. For each specimen, two tests have been considered: a first one with the microphone set back by 20 mm from the duct wall, and a second test with a 30 mm recessed sensor. Both configurations had a 10 mm insulating plug at the end of the cavity, flush mounted with the duct wall. The deviations in terms of amplitude and phase of the FRF between the DUT and the RM are shown in Figure 9 to Figure 12.

Looking at the configuration with a 20 mm cavity in front of the microphone (Figure 8 and 9), it is first of all clear the presence of two damped resonance peaks: the lowest frequency peak is linked to the $\frac{1}{4}\lambda$ resonance of the whole cavity in front of the microphone, while the second peak is probably linked to the $\frac{3}{4}\lambda$ resonance. It is worth noticing that with respect to the theoretical values predicted for an empty cavity, the peaks appear to be shifted toward the leftmost side of the frequency axis due to the damping provided by the insulator. Such results were confirmed by the preliminary investigation performed and discussed in [12] where simple analytical models were used to study the expected FRF at different system configurations.

For some specimens, the amplitude of the transfer function oscillates around 0 dB (no deviations from the RM), and the maximum discrepancy remains always below 4 dB, except for the specimen #2, which has the highest density and shows an excessive attenuation in almost the entire examined frequency range.

A comparison among the FRFs denotes some expected features. For example, the FRF magnitude curves preserve the same common trend, but the absolute values are shifted

depending on the density of the glass wool, and also the frequency response undergoes some modifications: the first peak is observed within the band from 2 kHz to 3 kHz, and it is shifted toward lowest frequencies when the damping of the system rises; the same applies to the second peak, which falls within the range between 9 kHz and 10 kHz.

Finally, it is possible to observe that for all specimens, the evolution of the phase is substantially overlapping.

Figure 9 Amplitude of the H01 with $L_p=10\text{mm}$ and $L_a=10\text{mm}$ by varying the density of the test specimen

Figure 10 Phase of the H01 with $L_p=10\text{mm}$ and $L_a=10\text{mm}$ by varying the density of the test specimen

As already mentioned, a second configuration has been investigated with a 30 mm cavity in front of the microphone, partially filled with GW in the first portion of 10 mm. This mounting system should provide some benefits in terms of thermal control capability, as expected from the analytical investigations carried out during the preliminary feasibility study. The amplitudes and phase of the FRF obtained in the test are illustrated in Figure 11 and Figure 12. The scenario is quite similar to the previous one, but some remarks are needed. In this case the lowest frequency peak is still linked to the $\frac{1}{4}\lambda$ resonance of the whole cavity, while the second one could be due to a $\frac{1}{2}\lambda$ resonance of the air-filled portion of the cavity. Except for the highest density test case, which shows again excessive attenuation over the entire frequency range, the first resonance presents minor deviations from the RM with respect to Figure 8, while for the second peak the discrepancies are higher.

Figure 11 Amplitude of the H01 with $L_p=10\text{mm}$ and $L_a=20\text{mm}$ by varying the density of the test specimen

Figure 12 Phase of the H01 with $L_p=10\text{mm}$ and $L_a=20\text{mm}$ by varying the density of the test specimen

CERAMIC FELT AND META-ARAMID FELT

Following the results achieved with the glass wool, other materials, such as ceramic felt and meta-aramid felt, have been examined. (Table 1)

Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the amplitude and phase of the FRF for the ceramic felt, respectively. Different lengths of cavity were tested and, as it can be observed, the case with no cavity behind the insulating material ($L_a=0$) gives the best results from the acoustic perspective but is of little importance due to its thermal control limitations. For all the investigated configurations, the thickness of the ceramic portion was kept equal to 10 mm.

Moving on to the meta-aramid felt, it was found that it is more difficult to install and its low machinability (it can be cut with scissors but tends to fall apart very easily) limits its capability to be perfectly adapted to the inner cavity of the holder. For this reason, it was decided to perform the tests also in another mounting configuration, having the internal cavities filled and sealed with some glass wool (see also Figure 2). It comes out clearly from Figure 15 and Figure 16 that the inclusion of the glass wool as sealing material strongly improved the repeatability of the tests but, in general, the meta-aramid felt proved to be inconvenient

for its poor acoustic properties, both with and without glass wool sealing, in comparison to glass wool. For this reason, it was decided to discard this material for future investigations.

Figure 13 Amplitude of the H01 for ceramic felt at different length of cavity

Figure 14 Phase of the H01 for ceramic felt at different length of cavity

Figure 15 Amplitude of the H01 for meta-aramid felt with and without glass wool around the microphone

Figure 16 Phase of the H01 for meta-aramid felt with and without glass wool around the microphone

MATERIALS COMPARISON

To summarize the main outcomes from the presented experimental activity, results obtained from all different configurations have been compared in Figure 17 and Figure 18. The results have been selected considering similar DUT arrangements, in order to have a coherent comparison. Results based on a 10 mm air filled cavity in front of the microphone have been selected because, from the preliminary heat exchange analyses and the acoustic results, it is expected to provide the best compromise between thermal insulation and acoustic sensitivity. For meta-aramid felt, such results are not available due to the already mentioned limitations encountered during the installation of the material in the holder, nevertheless valuable conclusions can be drawn. Figure 17 and Figure 18 confirm that the glass wool shows the lowest attenuation in the tested frequency band and depicts better acoustic results (i.e. smaller deviations from the RM response) than those obtained with the ceramic felt, which was tested with the same arrangement. As reported in the plots, two different densities of glass wool are considered because both show acceptable results and are worthy to be monitored. This selection is motivated by the fact that a density in between ρ_1 and ρ_3 could represent an even better solution. Of course, it is clear that the best configuration depends on the desired frequency band under investigation. The meta-aramid felt shows, up to 4 kHz, a pretty constant and limited attenuation which grows more and more by rising the frequency. Such attenuation is expected to increase even more if an air cavity is needed in front of the microphone to meet the thermal insulation requirements. These results let conclude that the DUT with glass wool shows the best behavior and is the most promising design solution.

Figure 17 Amplitude comparison of examined materials

Figure 18 Phase comparison of examined materials

CONCLUSION

The experimental characterization of acoustic liners under working conditions representative of the turbine exhaust (high flow speed and temperature) is a challenging research topic. The well-known experimental methodology for the impedance estimation relies on grazing flow rigs with dedicated acoustic instrumentation which has to be protected from the thermally hostile environment. Different strategies can be deployed to this purpose, and one of them exploits the recession of the microphones, similarly to what is done to reduce the aerodynamic pressure fluctuations.

The hypothesized system adopts microphones recessed inside cylindrical cavities partially filled by an insulating material, with the dual purpose of thermally insulating the microphone and damping resonances in the frequency response of the system.

Following the results obtained from preliminary numerical analyses, a system configuration has been conceived and its performance has been experimentally evaluated. To this purpose, a test bench has been designed and manufactured to allow the measurement of the frequency response of several measurement solutions, having different cavity geometries, different thicknesses

and types of interposed insulating materials, namely glass wool, meta-aramid felt and ceramic felt.

As indicated by the analytical models and confirmed by the tests, the system transfer functions are characterized by resonances whose peaks move and vary in amplitude as the geometry of the system and the characteristics of the insulation material change. The configurations that depicted the best results are those with a 20 mm recessing microphone and 10 mm of glass wool.

The results are such as to encourage further investigations of the method. In particular, it is necessary to understand its effectiveness in the presence of flow and the impact of even higher working temperature. As a consequence of higher working temperature, the analytical model indicates that a decrease in the resistivity to the air flow of the material is expected and, therefore, a response of the system characterized by a lower damping. Further, since an increase of the temperature leads to a higher speed of sound, this should allow to increase the thickness of the porous material and the length of the air cavity.

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